

1 Helminthic host defense peptides: using the parasite to defend the host

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18

19 Abstract

20 Parasitic helminths are destined to share niches with a variety of microbiota that inevitably
21 influences their interaction with the host. To modulate the microbiome for their benefit, and
22 defend against pathogenic isolates, helminths have developed host defense peptides and
23 proteins (HDP) as integral elements of their immunity. These often exert a relatively non-
24 specific membranolytic activity toward bacteria, sometimes with limited or no toxicity toward
25 host cells. With a few exceptions, such as nematode cecropin-like peptides and antibacterial
26 factors, helminthic HDP are largely underexplored. This review intends to scrutinize current
27 knowledge on the repertoire of such peptides in helminths and promote their research as
28 potential leads for an anti-infective solution to the burgeoning problem of antibiotic resistance.

29

30 **Host defense peptides: traits and roles**

31 Host defense peptides (HDP), often referred to as antimicrobial peptides (AMP) (**Box 1**) are
32 gene-encoded, multifunctional effector molecules of innate immunity, with direct
33 antimicrobial activity and/ or immunomodulatory properties [1]. Thousands have been
34 reported to be variously active against Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria and
35 mycota, sometimes displaying antiviral, antiparasitic, or antiprotozoal activities [2]. In
36 addition, HDP can have a pleiotropic role in the host immunity of higher organisms,
37 modulating the activity of immune cells in inflammatory processes and stimulating cell
38 proliferation in angiogenesis or wound healing, which currently garners as much interest as
39 their direct antibacterial activities [3]. They are ubiquitously produced throughout the tree of
40 life; in fungi, algae, and plants as well as invertebrate and vertebrate animals, where they are
41 mainly expressed in immune cells and epithelia. A compendium of databases dealing with
42 HDP of various types and origins is shown in **Box 2**.

43 HDP have acted at the front line of innate host defense throughout the evolution of animals,
44 adapting to the pressure of a constantly changing microbial challenge. Consequently, they
45 have an extraordinary degree of structural diversity and are usually classified into four classes
46 according to their primary and secondary structures; *i*) α helical, *ii*) β sheet, *iii*) $CS\alpha\beta$ and *iv*)
47 non- $\alpha\beta$ peptides with extended conformation, of which *ii*) and *iii*) are cysteine bridge
48 stabilized (CS) (**Figure 1**) [1,4–6]. Their active structures and physico-chemical properties
49 have mostly been related to their interaction with microbial membranes, while interactions
50 with other microbial cell-wall or intracellular components are less considered [3], even
51 though some HDP have intracellular elements as their principal targets (e.g., nucleic acids,
52 ribosomal machinery) [7]. Accordingly, HDP are further classified as membrane-active
53 (membranolytic) or non-lytic. Their relationship with the membrane bilayer and bacterial
54 outer wall components is in any case complex and difficult to discern.

55 As a result of a widespread membrane-centric attitude to HDP, their most studied attributes
56 are charge, hydrophobicity, and amphipathicity. The charge can range significantly (although
57 roughly around +6 is most frequent [5]) and drives electrostatic interactions with anionic
58 bacterial membranes as an essential first step towards insertion and disruption. Importantly, it
59 contributes to selectivity for anionic microbial membranes against the more neutral and
60 cholesterol-rich ones of host cells. Membrane insertion requires residues to be arranged or
61 repositioned so that apolar side chains contact the lipid bilayer, which is when hydrophobicity
62 and amphipathicity come into play. Apolar residues commonly form around 50% of the HDP
63 primary structure and their sidechains are often spatially separated from polar ones in their
64 secondary structure. Altering these three attributes can improve potency and/ or selectivity,
65 but generally with opposing effects [5].

66

67 **Therapeutic potential of helminthic HDP**

68 One of the driving forces behind HDP research over the past few decades is their potential for
69 treating microbial infections, in particular those from **multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria**
70 (see **Glossary**). Up to now, ~3000 peptides have been identified as antibacterial (see APD
71 database, **Box 2**), mainly from animals (in particular anurans, see DADP database, **Box 2**). The
72 transition from *in vitro* to clinical applications has proven difficult, with most HDP-based drugs
73 failing before, or during clinical trials [8], even though the high manufacturing costs that are
74 disadvantageous with respect to the production of small-molecule antibiotics, can be mitigated
75 using appropriate expression platforms [9]. The Therapeutic Protein Database (see **Box 2**), a
76 subset of the Drugs@FDA database, lists hundreds of peptide and protein therapeutics but only
77 six anti-infective peptides in clinical use (e.g., daptomycin and gramicidin D), none of which
78 are derived from gene-encoded HDP. Drug Bank 5.0 [10] cites approximately 60 peptide-based
79 drugs, but mostly for the treatment of non-infective diseases.

80 A low alleged propensity to elicit resistance is often cited as one of the main advantages of
81 HDP, although resistance cannot be completely avoided and occurs similarly to conventional
82 antibiotics [11,12]. The multimodal action of HDP is however thought to confer an advantage,
83 making resistance expensive for the bacterial cell and therefore only transient. One major
84 obstacle to their therapeutic use is that HDP activity and stability are markedly affected by
85 physiological conditions, especially for the small, linear HDP. This can be mitigated by
86 cyclization (via cystine or backbone bridging) as occurs naturally in some HDP classes (e.g.,
87 α -, β -, and θ -defensins, β -hairpin peptides) (**Figure 1**) [13], or in part avoided by limiting their
88 use to topical application. Another major obstacle is their toxicity, as potent antibacterial
89 activity is often accompanied by unwanted side effects toward host cells. Although this can be
90 attenuated to some extent by altering their physico-chemical properties or by
91 nanoencapsulation, there is generally a trade-off between reduced toxicity and potency.

92 In this respect, some relatively short helminthic HDPs (e.g., anisaxins), which show potent
93 antimicrobial activity *in vitro* but remarkably low cyto- and genotoxicity towards host cells,
94 appear promising [5]. Their unexpected harmlessness towards the host, if inferred also in other
95 parasitic HDP, could play a significant role in future HDP prospecting for clinical use. Driven
96 by a rapid reciprocal adaptation to the selective pressures exerted between the host and the
97 parasite, which would favor the development of parasitic compounds that are minimally
98 detrimental to the host, low toxicity is a desired and distinctive feature of the helminthic HDP.

99

100 **Role of HDP in the innate immunity of parasitic helminths**

101 *Parasites - host - microbiome interactions*

102 The tripartite interaction between the helminth, its host, and the host microbiome
103 (conceptualized in the **holobiont**) starts with a complex exchange of chemical cues between

104 ligands and cognate receptors encompassed within different cellular pathways. Helminths
105 express these cues in different tissues, such as in neural and epithelial cells of the
106 gastrointestinal tract [14,15], or anal and esophageal excretory glands and tegumentum [16],
107 discharging them as **excretory/secretory products (ESP)**, or packaged as cargo in excretory
108 vesicles (EV). They are delivered to host cells via intracellular pathways to polarize the host
109 immune response towards tolerance, as reviewed previously [17]. Cecropin-like HDPs and
110 immunomodulatory cystatins are discharged directly as ESP or enveloped within EV
111 [15,18,19] to modulate the host microbiome with a direct antimicrobial effect or indirectly by
112 stimulating host immunity (**Figure 2, Key Figure**). Helminths sense microbial communities
113 and adapt their antibacterial activity, as shown by the expression of chitinase and lysozyme in
114 *Heligmosomoides polygyrus*, a small intestinal nematode, when exposed to the mouse
115 microbiome [20]. Marine zoonotic nematode *Anisakis pegreffii* changes the type and level of
116 HDP (anisaxins) expression dramatically depending on the host type and its physiological
117 activity (i.e., paratenesis and active migration) [6], while filarial nematode *Onchocerca ochengi*
118 releases different molecules with functional activity depending on the developmental stage of
119 the worm and the state of the host immune system [57].

120 This is evidently only a linear and simplified description of the intricate communication
121 occurring within the holobiont, and helminth HDPs are certainly not the only players shaping
122 bacterial communities. Analogous cues are contemporaneously exchanged by the host and
123 competitive bacterial taxa within the microbiome, and the basic understanding of the conditions
124 of this tripartite interaction and consequent HDP expression is still lacking. In other words, the
125 HDPs produced by the parasites and by the host and associated microbiota could be considered
126 as a sort of “**antimicrobial peptidome**”. Deciphering communication within the holobiont is
127 further complicated by downstream feedback effects that are difficult to model *in vitro*. This is
128 reflected by “*in vivo*” observations inferring opposite effects; from a contributing role of

129 helminths in human and animal dysbiosis, to a beneficial effect of helminths for the host
130 (reviewed in [21]). Initiatives aiming to disentangle the role of parasite-associated microbiota
131 on the pathophysiology of helminthiases are therefore welcome, as the Parasite Microbiome
132 Project, which furnishes the guidelines needed to overcome bottlenecks in the experimental
133 study design and strives to achieve repeatability and comparability among the studies [22].

134 Finally, the plasticity of helminths to colonize novel niches through the trophic chain (i.e., the
135 acquirement of a new parasite species by the accidental ingestion of infected prey) exposes
136 them to unfamiliar host-associated microbiota, in addition to an unknown proinflammatory
137 host response. Such selective pressure can drive the molecular diversification of helminth HDP
138 in the long run [23], resulting in the presence of multigene HDP families counting several
139 members, such as in the case of *A. pegreffii* anisaxins. It is intriguing to consider that mapping
140 of the evolutionary signatures in contemporary HDP could allow backtracking of different host
141 types (and their microbiotas) that have occurred during the habitat transitions of helminths, i.e.,
142 abandoning of terrestrial environment and colonization of aquatic bodies, or *vice versa* [24].
143 This is reinforced by the observation that most of the bidirectional transitions in nematodes
144 occurred in Clades 1-6, which are distinctive for their secretory-excretory system [24], one of
145 the sites of HDP production [23].

146

147 *Helminth innate immunity*

148 Lacking an adaptive immune system, nematodes and trematodes rely on the innate immune
149 defense that displays an intricate network of intracellular signaling pathways and secreted
150 molecules [25,26]. The arsenal of secreted proteins and peptides produced in response to, or
151 contemporaneously with the activation of the innate signaling pathways include immune
152 effectors aimed at the elimination of invading microbes [27], such as lysozymes and the C-type

153 lectin-domain containing protein clec-60 [28], and various types of HDPs. For example, the
154 over-expression of clec-60 via the gut-brain axis (enteric nervous system – central nervous
155 system) in *C. elegans* can protect the organism from bacterial infections through a route
156 coupling the evolutionarily conserved signaling mechanisms of the neuronal muscarinic
157 pathway and the epithelial Wnt pathway [29]. In the same species, other factors, such as
158 caenacin CNC-4, are produced through the mitochondrial unfolded protein response (UPR^{mt}),
159 a stress-activated pathway that initiates the expression of genes involved in the recovery of the
160 dysfunctional mitochondrion [30]. However, innate immunity strategies and resulting HDP in
161 free-living helminths might undertake a different route than in the parasitic helminths. While
162 the digestion of bacterial communities that are a food source for *C. elegans* is assisted via
163 secreted HDPs [31,32], for the parasitic helminths that do not feed upon bacteria, host-associate
164 microbiota might pose a challenge, in addition to the host's immune effectors.

165 This would suggest that the immune response in free-living vs parasitic helminths may be based
166 on significantly different mechanisms. In that sense, an *in silico* phylogenetic approach to
167 nematode immunity focusing on the “quality and quantity” of antimicrobial peptides and
168 proteins has not evidenced the existence of an archetypal nematode HDP repertoire [32]. While
169 this can be partially explained by a remarkable helminth genomic diversity characterized by
170 the widespread presence of orphan gene families with unclear or untraceable ancestry [33], it
171 necessitates *in vitro* mechanistic assessment of specific HDP families.

172 The helminth-associated microbiome can include a range of obligate and facultative taxa, but
173 the regulatory involvement of HDPs is poorly understood, except to some extent in filarial
174 nematodes (*Brugia malayi*, *Loa loa*, *Onchocerca volvulus*, *Wuchereria bancrofti*). The latter
175 harbor the intracellular bacteria *Wolbachia* that is transmitted via their insect intermediate
176 hosts, and regulate the endosymbiont by autophagy [34] rather than by secretion of intracellular
177 HDP. This implies that filarial HDP do not distinguish between *Wolbachia* and other bacterial

178 taxa, and their damaging of the endosymbiont would consequently reduce nematode
179 reproductive success and fitness. Similarly, insects, in which *Wolbachia* is a maternally
180 inherited endosymbiotic modulator of reproduction that generally improves their fitness and
181 primes their immune system, do not express intracellularly-acting HDP [35]. Although the
182 mechanisms of filarial HDP regulation remain elusive, it has been demonstrated that *Wolbachia*
183 can activate host genes encoding secreted HDP to protect the insect from additional pathogenic
184 infection [36]. Interestingly, in the mosquito, *Aedes aegypti*, cecropins and other HDPs are
185 highly upregulated and prevent infection by filarial nematodes [37], but this comes at the cost
186 of halving the host's life span.

187 For other nematodes, the intimate crosstalk between the core-microbiota and helminth
188 immunity is less well explored, despite the major consequences that the presence of a bacterium
189 might exert on the helminth's final hosts. For example, *Neorickettsia* colonizes cells in the
190 reproductive tissues of the trematode *Fasciola hepatica*, transmitting vertically via the eggs to
191 conspecifics, or horizontally to trematode-infected hosts, such as humans, horses, and dogs,
192 where it exacerbates fatal septicemia [38].

193 Finally, *in vitro* experiments might represent a starting point for the study of helminth
194 immunity. *Anisakis simplex* stimulated *in vitro* with *E. coli* LPS failed to activate pathways
195 homologous to those of *C. elegans* immunity, nor did it express HDP, but rather proteins that
196 engage in interactions with host immunity [39]. Despite the nematode's inability to recognize
197 LPS through PAMPs, we speculate that as this is a conserved Gram-negative bacterial cell
198 wall motif, it is nonetheless perceived through some other anisakid mechanism(s). In the gut
199 environment, rather than affecting *Anisakis* immune response directly, LPS primarily warns
200 the nematode to expect a host innate response and react via the production of
201 immunomodulatory products. In contrast, peptides with solely immunomodulatory properties
202 (HDM, **Box 1**), such as *F. hepatica* FhHDM-1, bind and neutralize LPS released by intestinal

203 flora or microbial co-infection, subduing LPS-mediated activation of host macrophages and
204 protecting gut integrity by providing an anti-inflammatory environment. This mitigates the
205 effects of damage to the intestinal epithelium caused by the infecting parasite, preventing
206 luminal bacterial toxins (LPS) from entering into circulation [40]. Furthermore, macrophages
207 can internalize FhHDM-1 and localize it to the endolysosome, where a released fragment
208 inhibits v-ATPases required for the acidification of lysosomal vesicles [41]. This interferes
209 with antigen processing, preventing these antigen-presenting cells from upscaling the
210 immune reaction.

211

212 **Inventory of helminthic HDP**

213 To date, ~20 AMP families have been identified and reported in different species within the
214 Nematoda and Platyhelminthes [41–45]. However, only a handful of defense-related peptides
215 has been identified in parasitic helminths (**Table 1**), and even fewer have been functionally
216 characterized (**Supplementary Table S1**). We will discuss the best-characterized examples in
217 the following sections, provisionally grouping HDP according to their origins (i.e., helminth
218 phylum).

219

220 *Flatworm HDP*

221 The most relevant HDP identified in flatworms are helminth host defense molecules (HDM),
222 such as *Fasciola hepatica* FhHDM-1. These α -helical peptides exclusively found in trematodes
223 (**Supplementary Table S2**), have immunomodulatory activities and can also bind to, and
224 neutralize bacterial LPS. A structural similarity to helical vertebrate cathelicidins has been
225 suggested, but unlike these, they are devoid of direct antimicrobial activity [41]. Another HDP
226 uniquely found in flatworms is *Schistosoma mansoni* SmDLP (dermaseptin-like peptide),

227 which derives its name from the strong similarity with the α -helical frog dermaseptins. It has
228 antimicrobial activity against some Gram-positive bacteria and fungi but is more notably
229 hemolytic [44]. Four HDP from the schistocin family that belong to the **cryptide** class of HDP,
230 have been identified in the same species [45]. They also all conform to an α -helical
231 conformation in a membrane-like environment and are active against Gram-positive and -
232 negative bacteria as well as fungi, to some extent.

233

234 *Helminthic cecropins*

235 Cecropin peptides have been identified in insects, nematodes, tunicates, and bacteria and were
236 first isolated from the hemolymph of the lepidopteran *Hyalophora cecropia* [43,46]. In
237 helminths, they have a narrow taxonomical distribution, restricted to clade III nematodes, and
238 more specifically to Ascarididae [47] (**Supplementary Table S2**). Those that have been
239 functionally characterized so far belong to *Ascaris suum* (cecropin-P1, -P2, -P3, and -P4) and
240 other Ascarididae, namely *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Toxocara canis* (**Table 1**) [43,48]. They
241 are synthesized as pre-pro-peptides containing signal sequence, a positively charged mature
242 region, and an anionic pro-sequence. Mature peptides are relatively short, rich in serine, and
243 fold to a linear and amphipathic α -helix in an anisotropic environment (**Figure 1**). Cecropins
244 are potentially bactericidal, with activity against Gram-negative and -positive bacteria at low
245 to moderate micromolar concentrations, and in some cases at sub-micromolar concentrations
246 (e.g., cecropin-P1 against Gram-negative bacteria) [43,48]. They are far less potent against the
247 fungi *Candida albicans* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, with minimal inhibitory concentration
248 (MIC) of 200-300 μ M [48]. Cecropins, as the majority of amphipathic α -helical HDP [5], are
249 membrane-active and pore-forming peptides. Initial interaction with the membrane occurs via

250 C-terminal α -helical segment, and subsequent steps involve pore or lesions formation resulting
251 in cell death.

252 More recently, HDP belonging to this family have also been identified in *Anisakis* spp., thus
253 named anisaxins (anisaxin-1, -2S, -2P, -3, and -4) [49]. They are also synthesized as pre-pro-
254 peptides, while the mature HDP are cationic and moderately amphipathic α -helical peptides.
255 All anisaxins showed excellent antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria
256 (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter*
257 *baumannii*) at sub-micromolar or low micromolar concentrations, including multidrug-
258 resistant isolates. Activity against a representative of Gram-positives (*Staphylococcus aureus*)
259 was somewhat weaker, but still at appreciable low to moderate micromolar concentrations [49].
260 These peptides are also membrane-active, inducing pore formation by extracting the lipids from
261 the membrane. Interestingly, they show some similarity in their action to the bee venom peptide
262 melittin, causing strong molecular leakage without strongly affecting the bacterial cell surface
263 morphology. Unlike the highly toxic melittin, anisaxins effect on human cells was negligible,
264 with LC₅₀ values (50% lethality concentration) normally well over 100 μ M. Even for the most
265 lytic anisaxins (A-1 and A-3), the LC₅₀ (78 and 21 μ M, respectively) was significantly higher
266 than the bactericidal concentrations.

267

268 *Helminthic antibacterial factors (ABFs)*

269 ABFs belong to the cis-defensins superfamily, whose typical cysteine-stabilized α -helix and β -
270 sheet fold (CS $\alpha\beta$ fold) has been acquired by ancestral, derived, or convergent evolution by
271 several invertebrate, plant, and fungal HDPs, including invertebrate defensins [86]. ABFs have
272 been identified in several nematode species, including *A. suum* (AsABF- α , β , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ), *A.*
273 *lumbricoides* (corresponding to AsABF- β and $-\gamma$), and *Ancylostoma duodenale* (Ad-ABF)

274 (Table 1) [43,50–52], but display a relatively narrow taxonomical distribution, restricted to
275 clade III and V roundworms (Supplementary Table S2), as previously reported by Tarr [47].
276 The typical CS $\alpha\beta$ fold of ABFs is stabilized by three disulfide bonds, with the fourth
277 contributing to stapling a strand outside this motif (see Figure 1), with the exception *A. suum*
278 As-ABF-6Cys- α that has only three disulphide bridges [52]. To our knowledge, only As-ABFs
279 have been screened for antimicrobial activity, and in contrast to cecropins, showed to be more
280 potent against Gram-positive bacteria (at submicromolar or even low nanomolar
281 concentrations). Activity against Gram-negative bacteria and fungi was in some cases (e.g.,
282 against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Kluyveromyces thermotolerans*) at low micromolar
283 concentrations, but it was generally reduced compared to activity against Gram-positives.
284 ABFs activity is hindered by the presence of the salts [43,53], as is the case for many other
285 HDP, especially defensins [5], stalling the progress of these peptides toward clinical
286 applications.

287

288 *Other nematode HDP*

289 Similar to cis-defensins, a few other HDP families have an ancient inferred evolutionary origin
290 and display a broad distribution in metazoans. Among these, macins are present in nematode
291 (but not in flatworm) genomes and might be specifically restricted to clade V nematodes
292 (Supplementary Table S2). Although they still require functional characterization, these
293 cysteine-rich peptides may represent attractive targets for future research due to the combined
294 antimicrobial and tissue regeneration properties of their homologs in other invertebrates [54].
295 Notably, another HDP class that displays a similarly broad taxonomic distribution, i.e., big
296 defensins, which are representative members of the trans-defensins structural superfamily,
297 have been entirely lost during helminth evolution [55] (Supplementary Table S2).

298 Other types of host defense peptides or proteins were first identified in *C. elegans* and
299 subsequently found in several other nematodes. Among these, nemapores are small proteins
300 with a cystine-stabilized helix-rich structure, that resemble membranolytic amoebapores. The
301 best characterized are *C. elegans* caenopores, with a broad-spectrum activity against Gram-
302 positive and -negative bacteria. Caenacins and neuropeptide-like proteins (NLPs) are glycine-
303 rich polypeptides with non- $\alpha\beta$ structures. Finally, an additional three peptides have been
304 identified in the filarial nematode *Onchocerca ochengi*, with reported antibacterial and
305 antiplasmodial activity. These showed some similarity with human dermcidin and galectin, and
306 unlike most other HDPs are anionic [42].

307

308 **Computation approaches for the discovery of novel helminthic HDP**

309 During the last decade, helminth genomics has greatly benefited from the technological
310 advancements in DNA sequencing technologies, which have so far allowed the release of 161
311 nematode and 53 flatworm genomes, most of which are obligate endoparasites (NCBI
312 genome data, as of February 2023) [56]. Although Nematoda and Platyhelminthes present the
313 highest rates of gene loss among Metazoa [57], they are both characterized by a very high
314 level of genetic novelty, displaying several lineage-specific expanded gene families [33]
315 acquired through evolutionary mechanisms likely linked to host adaptation [57].

316 Interestingly, many of these expansions concern ESP that may play important effector roles
317 during host-parasite interactions, for example by protecting the helminth itself from bacterial
318 and fungal infections (e.g., lysozymes in clade IVa and Va/ Vc nematodes) [33]. Notably,
319 helminth genomes encode a high number of short, secreted peptides that, despite lacking
320 detectable homology with other metazoan sequences, show physico-chemical properties
321 consistent with a potential antimicrobial function.

322 Several **machine learning**-based computational pipelines have been recently developed to
323 aid the discovery of novel HDP through the application of artificial intelligence, providing a
324 faster and cost-effective alternative to classical biochemical isolation approaches. Unlike
325 BLAST, such methods do not require the detection of sequence homology for the
326 identification of candidate HDP, relying on the identification of primary sequence features
327 shared by a training set of peptides with known antimicrobial activity, but uncommon in
328 peptides with other biological functions. While an in-depth overview of these methods goes
329 beyond the scope of this review (for a comprehensive description, see [58–60]), several
330 recent publications showcase the potential of machine learning approaches in the discovery of
331 novel HDP in non-model invertebrates [61–63]. It is however important to remark that no
332 matter the level of sophistication that the current computational approaches utilize, laboratory
333 functional validation remains a fundamental confirmatory step for any candidate HDP. Two
334 recent examples of computer-assisted HDP discovery concerns schistocins in the blood fluke
335 *S. mansoni* [64] and a large family of novel cestode HDPs yet to be named [65], whose
336 antimicrobial activity was validated *in vitro*. Schistocins were identified with *encrypted*, a
337 novel machine learning algorithm able to identify short active peptides embedded within
338 larger precursors (i.e., cryptides). On the other hand, the identification of cestode HDP was
339 based on a custom pipeline of analysis aimed at the discovery of peptides displaying
340 signatures that would point to the presence of an amphipathic helix.

341 Another interesting study carried out in the nematode *Teladorsagia circumcincta* combined
342 proteomics and bioinformatics screening to detect antimicrobial ESP in secreted EVs.

343 Although these peptides were not individually tested, the authors were able to demonstrate
344 the antimicrobial activity carried by EVs and ESP, validating the reliability of their approach
345 [66].

346 Despite these encouraging outputs, the computer-assisted identification of novel HDP in
347 helminths will remain a challenging task for the years to come, due to the variable quality of
348 available helminth genome assemblies, the different technical approaches used for
349 sequencing and assembly, the inherent complexity of these genomes and the risk of
350 exogenous contamination [67]. Moreover, machine learning approaches require a list of
351 known protein sequences as an input, which in the case of helminths often derives from
352 incomplete gene annotations. In other words, features that are expected to be shared by
353 lineage-specific HDP gene families, characterized by unusual architectures, and subjected to
354 strict regulation, are under-represented in helminths [68].

355 Undoubtedly, ongoing community efforts such as WormBase Parasite [56] will lead to
356 further improvements in the quality of –omic resources available for helminths in the next
357 few years, simplifying and amplifying the future identification of HDP in these organisms
358 [67].

359

360 **Concluding Remarks**

361 *In silico* helminthic resources are an ideal starting point for prospecting of parasitic HDP, as
362 helminthic genomes may hide lineage-specific HDP families that share no detectable
363 sequence homology with those previously described in other metazoans (e.g., *Taenia* sp.
364 HDP). However, these studies should be discouraged from leaving at that point, as
365 fragmented knowledge impedes firmly evaluating costs and benefits between HDP of
366 parasitic and free-living taxa. Surprisingly low toxicity and genotoxicity have been observed
367 in a few helminthic HDP but this is suspected to be more common due to the coevolution of
368 the “producer” with a host. This should be scrutinized with particular interest, as HDP
369 cytotoxicity is a major barrier to their clinical use. A large number of HDP isoforms present

370 in parasitic vs free-living genomes indicates their putative involvement in functions other
371 than only antimicrobial activity, representing a treasure trove for the identification of novel
372 bioactive compounds, as well as vaccine and drug targets. The apparent distinction of
373 peptides with prevailing immunomodulatory traits in flatworms (e.g., HDM) and prevailing
374 antimicrobial activity in nematode lineages is an interesting observation from the
375 evolutionary perspective, which might suggest that drivers other than just the host microbiota
376 exert pressure on the HDP evolution. However, this observation still needs to be tested over a
377 larger number of HDP families among helminths taxa (see **Outstanding questions**).

378

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385

386 **Declaration of interests**

387 The authors declare no competing interests.

388

389 **Resources**

390 ⁱ <https://aps.unmc.edu/>

391 ⁱⁱ <http://bactibase.hammamilab.org/main.php>

392 ⁱⁱⁱ <http://split4.pmfst.hr/dadp/>

393 ^{iv} <http://dramp.cpu-bioinfor.org/>

394 ^v <https://dbaasp.org/home>

395 ^{vi} <http://www.camp.bicnirrh.res.in/exLinks.php>

396 ^{vii} <https://bioinformatics.cs.ntou.edu.tw/ADAM/>

397 ^{viii} <http://yadamp.unisa.it/default.aspx>

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- 569

570 Glossary

571 **Antimicrobial peptidome:** HDP produced and secreted contemporarily by the parasite, the
572 host, and host/parasite-associated microbiota within the parasitization site.

573 **Cryptides:** antimicrobial peptide fragments encrypted within larger precursors proteins, whose
574 primary biological function is not necessarily related to immune defense.

575 **Excretory/secretory products (ESP):** include a broad range of proteins with different
576 functions but a shared presence of a signal peptide for secretion. In helminths, several ES
577 proteins are pathogenic determinants, which facilitate the entry of the pathogen in host tissues
578 or modulate the host immune response to prevent their elimination from the host.

579 **Holobiont:** an interactive community encompassing the host and other individual species
580 (bionts) living in, on, or around it. Since its original definition in the mid-20th century, the
581 concept evolved to include genomes of bionts contributing to the functioning of the whole,
582 with the coining of the term ‘holobiome’.

583 **Machine Learning algorithms:** multi-layered approaches that, when applied to the field of
584 bioinformatics, can learn features from a sequence dataset, allowing to make sophisticated
585 predictions when appropriately trained (e.g., determining the likelihood that an uncharacterized
586 query sequence has antimicrobial properties).

587 **Multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria:** bacteria that have become resistant to specific groups
588 of antibiotics, which therefore cannot be used to treat infections caused by these bacteria.

589

590 **Box 1. Correct use of terminology**

591 **AMP: Antimicrobial peptide**

- 592 - natural (gene encoded or enzyme synthesized) or synthetic
- 593 - having a direct antimicrobial activity, most often membranolytic
- 594 - include protein fragments with antimicrobial activity

595 **HDP: Host* defense peptide**

- 596 - gene encoded, endogenous peptides or proteins
- 597 - principally antimicrobial and sometimes with immunomodulatory activity

598 - can act by various mechanisms (membranolytic or intracellular targets)

599 **HDM: Helminth Defense Molecules**

600 - peptides or proteins

601 - having immunomodulatory activity on host*

602 - not membranolytic or directly antimicrobial

603 **IDR: Innate Defense Regulator**

604 - synthetic immunomodulatory versions of HDP

605 - not directly antimicrobial or membranolytic

606 * For HDP the host is the producer organism, for HDMs the infected host animal

607

608 **Box 2. Currently active AMP and related databases**

609 APD3 Antimicrobial Peptide Databaseⁱ

610 BACTIBASE Dedicated to bacteriocinsⁱⁱ

611 DADP Database of Anuran Defense Peptidesⁱⁱⁱ

612 DRAMP Data Repository of AMPs^{iv}

613 DBAASP Antimicrobial Activity & Structure of Peptides^v

614 CAMP_{R4} Collection of Anti-Microbial Peptides^{vi}

615 ADAM A Database of Anti-Microbial peptides^{vii}

616 YADAMP Yet Another Database of AMPs^{viii}

617 THPdb Therapeutic Protein Database^{ix}

618

619 **Table 1. Examples of peptides related to defense in free living and parasitic nematodes and trematodes reported in primary scientific**
620 **literature.**

Family (Type)	Structure	Peptide	Nematode (Type)	Effect	Target	Location	Ref.
Host defense molecule (HDM)	α -helical	FhHDM-1	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	LPS-binding immunomodulatory	Not directly antimicrobial	ESP	[41]
Dermaseptin-like (HDP, DLP)	α -helical	SmDLP	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	membranolytic	weak antimicrobial hemolytic	ESP	[44]
Schistocins (Cryptide)	α -helical	Schistocin (1, 2, 3, 3.1)	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	membranolytic	G+ bacteria > G- & fungi	unknown	[45]
Cecropins-P (HDP, cecropin-like)	α -helical	Cecropin-P (P1, P2, P3, P4)	<i>Ascaris</i> spp. <i>Toxocara canis</i>	membranolytic	G+ & G- bacteria	ESP (EV)	[43,48]
Anisaxins (HDP, cecropin-like)	α -helical	Anisaxin (1, 2S, 2P, 3, 4)	<i>Anisakis</i> spp. (parasitic)	membranolytic	G- > G+ bacteria	ESP ¹	[49]
Antibacterial factors (HDP, defensin-like)	CS $\alpha\beta$	AsABF (8Cys α , β , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ 6Cys- α)	<i>Ascaris</i> spp. (parasitic)	membranolytic	G+ > G- bacteria, fungi	ESP	[43,50,69,70]
Antibacterial factors (HDP, defensin-like)	CS $\alpha\beta$	ABF (1-6)	<i>C. elegans</i> (free-living)	membranolytic	G+ > G- bacteria, fungi	ESP	[71]

Nemapores (HDP, amoebapore-like)	CS- α helix	Caenapores	<i>C. elegans</i> + 46 other nematode spp.	membranolytic digestion	G- & G+ bacteria	ESP ¹	[47]
Caenacins & NLP (HDP, gly-rich)	Non- $\alpha\beta$ extended	CNC, NLP (several)	<i>C. elegans</i> + other nematodes		G- & G+ bacteria, fungi	ESP ¹	[30,72]
ES Peptides (anionic HDP)	Unknown Unknown	ALT-1 (dermcidin-like) Galectin-like	<i>Onchocerca ochengi</i>	unknown	G-	ESP ²	[42]
Antimicrobial factors (unknown)	unknown	unknown Peroxidoxin-2	<i>Heligiosomoides</i> <i>polygyrus</i>	unknown	G+ & G- bacteria	ESP	[20]

621 ¹Predicted from presence of signal sequence; ² Predicted from *in vitro* experiments; ABF, antibacterial factor; ALT-1, abundant larval transcript-1 protein; CNC, caenacin; CS, cysteine bridge
622 stabilized; DPL, dermaseptin-like peptide; ES, excretory/ secretory; ESP, excretory/secretory products; EV, extracellular vesicle; HDM, helminth defense molecule; HDP, host defense peptide;
623 LPS, lipopolysaccharide, NPL, neuropeptide-like protein.

624

625 **Figure 1. An overview of major structural classes of antimicrobial peptides.** Structure
 626 coordinates for the chosen examples were downloaded from Protein Data Bank (PDB IDs:
 627 cecropin-P1, 2n92; thanatin, 8tfv, As-ABF- α , 2n56 and bovine indolicidin, 1g89).
 628 Visualization was by PyMOL 1.8 (SourceForge, CA) and coloring is according to secondary
 629 structure (cyan - α helical, magenta - β sheet, light pink - loop; yellow - disulphide bridge).
 630 *NB: the 'classic' CS $\alpha\beta$ fold is considered to include fungal, plant, and invertebrate defensins.
 631 Mammalian α - and θ - defensins belong to the β -sheet Class, along with β -hairpin peptides.
 632 Vertebrate β -defensins have a CS $\alpha\beta$ scaffold that is structurally different to and may be
 633 evolutionarily unrelated to the invertebrate one. As-ABF- α , *Anisakis suum* antibacterial factor-
 634 α ; CS, cysteine bridge stabilized; Pro, proline; S-S, disulfide; Trp, tryptophane.

635

636

637 **Figure 2, Key Figure. Schematic representation of the mechanism of action of helminthic**
638 **HDP.** During parasitization, helminths (1) release host defense peptides as a part of the total
639 excretory/secretory products (ESP) or packaged in extracellular vesicles (EV) (2). HDP serve
640 to modulate the host microbiome with a direct antimicrobial effect, or indirectly by stimulating
641 host immunity. They act principally, but not exclusively at the anionic bacterial membrane
642 surface, to which they are electrostatically attracted, as they are generally cationic (3). HDP
643 may be unstructured and adopt a defined conformation only at the membrane, allowing
644 insertion into the lipid bilayer, or they may already have a well-defined structure in bulk
645 solution. Structuring, often associated with oligomerization, is required to allow insertion into
646 the lipid bilayer (4). Once inserted into the membrane, the peptide may cause membrane
647 permeabilization in various ways, via the formation of discrete pores, less well-defined
648 aggregate channels, or simply by a detergent-like effect leading to membrane micellization (5).
649 Non-lytic peptides instead, access protein transport systems and internalize without membrane
650 lysis (6). The accumulation of HDP on the cell surface will cause interference with, and damage
651 to vital membrane protein machinery (7). Once HDP access the cytoplasm, they can also
652 interfere with internal protein machinery and/ or nucleic acids (8). HDP, host defense peptides;
653 ESP, excretory/secretory products; EV extracellular vesicles.

654

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